

A New Communic Acid Derivative from *Chromolaena collina* (DC) K. et R†.

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The aerial parts of *Chromolaena collina* contain besides known compounds a new diterpenic acid, 7β-acetoxy-trans-communic acid (4), the unsubstituted acid also being present. The chemotaxonomical situation in this genus therefore still remaining complicated.

FROM the genus *Chromolaena* up to now 5 species have been investigated chemically. Besides flavones^{1,2} some triterpenes³ and several sesquiterpenes of different types^{3,4} have been isolated so far. Therefore the chemotaxonomical situation still is not very clear. To learn more about the importance of the constituents in this genus a further species, *Chr. collina* (DC) K. et R. has been investigated.

The aerial parts of this species from Guatemala contain germacrene D (1) β-caryophyllenepoxide (2), trans-(+)-communic acid (3)⁵ and a further acid showing the molecular formula C₂₂H₃₂O₄, elucidated by high resolution mass spectroscopy. All spectral data clearly show that we are dealing with an acid, which has a further acetoxy group. The ¹H-NMR-data are very similar to those of 3⁶. Therefore it was very probable that the new acid is an acetoxy derivative of 3. Using decoupling experiments and taking in mind the variation in chemical shifts of the 17-H signals in the spectrum of 3 and those of the new acid (see table) only the 7β-position for the acetoxy-group is possible, therefore the structure should be 4. Though the absolute configuration has not been proved with certainty the isolation of trans-(+) communic acid with known absolute stereochemistry makes it very probable that 4 has the same one.

The roots of *Chr. collina* also contain 1 and 3. 3 and related acids up to now in Compositae only have been found in *Mikania* species⁷. The constituents isolated now still do not clarify the chemotaxonomical situation in the genus *Chromolaena*. Surely much more species have to be investigated to see which compounds are really important in this connection.

¹H-NMR-DATA OF 4 AND 5
(270 MHz, TMS AS INTERNAL STANDARD, δ-VALUES)

	4 (CDCl ₃)	5 (C ₆ D ₆)
3α-H		d(br) 1.94
3β-H		ddd 0.87
6α-H	dd 2.54	dd 2.60
6β-H	d(br) 2.23	d(br) 2.01
7α-H	s(br) 5.51	s(br) 5.63
11-H	dd(br) 2.45	m 2.3-2.4
11'-H		
12-H	t(br) 5.39	t(br) 5.53
14-H	dd 6.32	dd 6.53
15 _o -H	d 4.89	d 4.97
15 _ε -H	d 5.05	d 5.13
16-H	s(br) 1.76	s(br) 1.73
17-H	s(br) 4.86	s(br) 4.88
17'-H	s(br) 4.66	s(br) 4.73
18-H	s 0.99	s 1.16
19-H	s 1.31	s 1.08
OCH ₃	—	s 3.26
OAc	s 1.91	s 1.77

J (Hz): 2α, 3β=3α, 3β=14; 2β, 3β=4; 6α, 6β=14; 6α, 7α=3; 11, 12=7; 14, 15_o=11; 14, 15_ε=17. Irradiation at 7α-H sharpens the signal of 17-H and that of 6α-H forms a doublet (*J*=14); irradiation of the 12-H signal decouples the signals of 11-H and sharpens that of 16-H.

† Part 131. in the series "Naturally occurring Terpene-Derivatives"; for part 130. see: Bohlmann, F. and Mahanta, P. K. *Phytochemistry*, 1978, 17, 565.

Experimental

IR : Beckman IR 9, CCl_4 ; $^1\text{H-NMR}$: Bruker WH 270, δ -values, TMS as internal standard; MS : Varian MAT 711, 70 eV; optical rotation : Perkin-Elmer-polarimeter, CHCl_3 .

The air-dried plant-material (voucher RMK 7318) was extracted with ether-petrol (1:2) and the resulting extracts have been separated first by SC (sigel, act. grade II) and further by TLC (sigel, GF 254) using ether-petrol-mixtures as solvents. 50 g of roots afforded 1 (14 mg) and 3 (18 mg). 75 g of aerial parts yielded 1 (43 mg), 2 (11 mg), 3 (112 mg) and 4 (19 mg) (ether-petrol 1:1). 4 was esterified by CH_3N_2 in ether to give 5, which also was purified by TLC (ether-petrol 1:3).

7 β -Acetoxy-trans-communic acid (4) : Colorless oil, IR : CO_2H 3500-2400, 1695; OAc 1740; $\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$ 900 cm^{-1} . MS : M^+ m/e 350. 230 (2%) (calc. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4$ 360.230); M^+ -AcOH 300 (23); 300 - $\cdot\text{CH}_3$ 285 (8); 300 - $\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ 255 (8); $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CHC}(\text{CH}_3)=\text{CHCH}_2^+$ 81 (100); H_3CCO^+ 43 (85).

$$[\alpha]_{24}^{\lambda} = \frac{489 \quad 578 \quad 546 \quad 436 \quad 365 \text{ nm}}{-0.4 \quad -0.4 \quad -1.2 \quad -7.2 \quad -15.9^{\circ}} \quad (c=1.75)$$

Acknowledgement

We thank the "Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft" for supporting this investigation and Dr. R. King, Smithsonian Institution, Washinton, for the plant material.

References

1. G. FERRARO and J. CUSSIO, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, 12, 1825.
2. S. K. TALAPATRA, D. BHAR and B. TALAPATRA, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, 13, 284.
3. F. BOHLMANN and C. ZDERO, *Chem. Ber.*, 1977, 110, 487.
4. F. BOHLMANN and L. FIEDLER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1978, 111, 408.
5. V. P. ARYA, H. ERDTMAN and T. KUBOTA, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 16, 255.
6. F. BOHLMANN and C. ZDERO, *Chem. Ber.*, 1974, 107, 1416.
7. F. BOHLMANN, A. A. NATU and P. K. MAHANTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1978, 17, 483.